

Healing of acute anterior cruciate ligament rupture on MRI and outcomes following non-surgical management with the Cross Bracing Protocol

Article summary

The purpose of this study was to examine evidence of anterior cruciate ligament (ACL) healing based on MRI, patient-reported outcomes, and knee stability in individuals with acute ACL ruptures who were treated nonoperatively with the Cross Bracing Protocol (CBP).

The study included 80 patients who were treated with CBP (4-week knee immobilization in a brace, gradual increase in range of motion, rehabilitation under the supervision of physiotherapists) and underwent MRI evaluation at 3 and 6 months. The ACLOAS scale and statistical tests (Mann-Whitney, χ^2) were used to analyze the functional and stability outcomes of the knee at 12 months. The mean age of the patients was 26 years, 39% were female, 49% had a meniscal injury.

The study results showed that at 3 months, 90% of patients showed signs of ACL healing (ACLOAS grade 1: 50%, grade 2: 40%, grade 3: 10%). Patients with better healing (ACLOAS 1) had higher Lysholm and ACLQOL scores, less knee laxity, and a higher rate of return to sports (92% vs. 64%). 14% of patients had a re-injury of the ACL.

The conclusion is that after management of acute ACL ruptures with the CBP, 90% of patients had evidence of ACL healing on MRI at 3 months. Better ACL healing was associated with better functional outcomes.

Figure 1

The study participants were 80 patients aged 10–58 years (mean 26 years) with confirmed ACL ruptures on MRI treated with CBP who presented to a Sydney sports medicine physician between 2016 and 2021. Twelve patients underwent remote consultations due to COVID-19 restrictions. They were eligible for CBP if they presented within 1 month of injury, had full function and were able to immobilise their knee. Patients with injuries requiring surgery or a history of thrombosis were excluded. Figure 1 also shows the turnover of participants during the study, the reasons for exclusion from CBP and the reasons for choosing ACLR (no participant selected rehabilitation as their only option).

Figure 2

Figure 2 shows examples of five patients with MRI healing of the ACL. At 3-month follow-up, 90% of patients (n=72) had a continuous ACL, including 50% with grade 1 ACLOAS and 40% with grade 2 ACLOAS. Six of eight patients with grade 3 ACLOAS had the ligament attached to the posterior cruciate ligament and lateral wall or to the lateral wall. In four patients, between 3 and 6 months, ACLOAS grade 1 changed to 0. One patient with ACLOAS grade 2 to 3, which was due to a subsequent injury.

Table 1

The table shows the measures of the outcome of the ACL healing and the patients' return to function. MRI scans at 3 and 6 months indicate the degree of ligament healing, with higher grades indicating poorer outcomes. Knee function was assessed using the Lysholm scale – scores above 94 indicate “excellent” and below 84 indicate poorer function. Knee-related quality of life was assessed using the ACLQOL questionnaire, with lower scores indicating poorer quality of life. Lachman and Pivot-Shift tests assess joint stability – more laxity indicates poorer stability. Return to sports were assessed at 12 months, which helps to assess full function. These measures provide a comprehensive assessment of healing, knee function, quality of life, and return to sports.

Table 2

Table 2 presents participant characteristics both for the entire group and by ACLOAS grade at 3-month MRI. At injury, the mean age of participants was 26 (10) years, 39% were female, and 49% had a concomitant meniscal tear. All patients who were treated with the CBP method allowed their data to be included in the study.

Table 3

The table shows that participants with ACLOAS grade 1 at 3 months had better Lysholm scale scores (98 vs. 94) and ACLQOL (89 vs. 70), indicating better knee function and quality of life. They also had more normal Lachman (100% vs. 60%) and pivot-shift (85% vs. 30%) scores and a higher rate of return to sport (92% vs. 62%). The difference in ACL re-tear was not statistically significant. Better ACL healing is associated with better knee function, joint stability, and a higher rate of return to sport.

Conclusion

The conclusion is that after management of acute ACL ruptures with the CBP, 90% of patients had evidence of ACL healing on MRI at 3 months. Improved ACL healing was associated with improved functional outcomes, such as improved knee function and reduced knee laxity, and a higher return to sport rate.

Authors:

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A/Prof Steph Filbay is an NHMRC Emerging Leadership Fellow, Dame Kate Campbell Fellow, and Principal Research Fellow at the University of Melbourne's Centre for Health, Exercise, and Sports Medicine. Drawing on her personal experience with ACL injury and extensive research, she is known for promoting evidence-based ACL injury management and improving patient outcomes. She has presented her work over 100 times in 10 countries, chaired international committees, supervised 28 researchers, and received multiple awards and grants. Recently, she was awarded an NHMRC Investigator Grant for research on ACL injury and knee osteoarthritis, and a MRFF Clinical Trials Activity grant for a trial comparing a new non-surgical ACL treatment with surgery. Her h-index is 25.

Mohammad Chaker Jomaa

Dr. Mohammad Jomaa is a Sport and Exercise Physician with a medical degree from Cardiff University (2012) and Fellowship with the Australasian College of Sport and Exercise Physicians (2022). He also holds postgraduate qualifications in Healthcare Leadership, Management, and Musculoskeletal Medicine. Before specializing in Sport and Exercise, he gained experience in Emergency, Trauma, and Rehabilitation Medicine in the UK and Australia. In private practice, Dr. Jomaa uses modern therapeutic and biologic agents, along with ultrasound-guided injections for injury and pain management. His interests include concussion management, injury treatment, and prevention through lifestyle modification.

Jane Rooney

Jane Rooney is a highly respected physiotherapist in Australia, one of only 45 to hold the highest clinical qualification as a Fellow of the Australian College of Physiotherapists (Specialist Sports Physiotherapist) since 2009. She is dedicated to giving back to the profession, serving as a facilitator and examiner for the College's Clinical Specialisation

program. Academically, she is an Associate Clinical Professor at Swinburne University, an Honorary Lecturer at Melbourne University, a guest lecturer at La Trobe University, and a member of the Post Graduate Advisory Committee. She is also a regular presenter for the Australian Physiotherapy Association.

Rohan Sabharwal

Rohan joined PRP Diagnostic Imaging in January 2010. He graduated from the University of NSW and completed his residency and radiology training at Westmead Hospital in Sydney. His areas of focus include Musculoskeletal & Sports Imaging, as well as minimally invasive musculoskeletal and spinal procedures. Rohan is actively involved in teaching radiology, orthopaedics, physiotherapy, and podiatry trainees. He has a strong passion for Sports Imaging and works as a radiologist for the Sydney Swans, NSW Waratahs, NSW & Australian Cricket, Sydney Roosters, and Rugby World Sevens. Rohan is also pursuing an interest in Cardiac CT and holds Level B (the highest level) specialist status in CT Coronary Angiography.

Andrew van den Heever

Andrew joined PRP Illawarra in August 2019. He completed his undergraduate studies at the University of Cape Town in 1991 and his postgraduate training in Radiology at Groote Schuur Hospital in 1999. Since 2000, he has worked as a full-time radiologist in private practice. Andrew specializes in musculoskeletal radiology and is a founding member of the South African Musculoskeletal Imaging group. His expertise includes orthopaedic and sports imaging. He has been an invited speaker at various congresses and has taught registrars at Groote Schuur and Tygerberg Hospitals in South Africa.

James Kazaglis

James is an APA Sports and Exercise Titled Physiotherapist, recognizing his specialized training and expertise in physiotherapy, particularly in managing sports injuries and exercise prescription. He has worked with athletes at all levels, from amateur to professional, with a focus on cricket, AFL, and rugby. Since 2015, James has provided support to the Sydney Swans Academy, including training, match day coverage, and team travel. In addition to his professional work, James enjoys playing various sports, has played cricket at Sydney University, competes in triathlons, and completed an Ironman Triathlon in 2013.

Justin Merlino

Justin Merlino (born 24 October 1985 or 10 December 1986) is an Australian athlete, specialising in the 110 metres hurdles.

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Journal

The British Journal of Sports Medicine (Impact Factor: 11,8) is a bi-monthly peer-reviewed journal that focuses on sports science, sports medicine, and sports physiotherapy. Published by the BMJ Group, it was founded in 1964. Karim M. Khan (University of British Columbia) served as editor-in-chief from 2008 to 2020, followed by Jonathan Drezner (University of Washington) who took over in January 2021. Since 2009, the journal has collaborated with the International Olympic Committee to produce consensus statements on key topics in sports injury prevention and elite sport. Recent statements have covered issues such as concussions in sport (the "Berlin guidelines"), relative energy deficiency, training load and injury, athlete mental health, and injury/illness surveillance, offering guidance for clinicians. British Journal of Sports Medicine (BJSM) is a multimedia portal for authoritative original research, systematic reviews, consensus statements and debate in sport and exercise medicine (SEM).